

SURE
SUSTAINABLE
RESILIENT
EU FARMING
SYSTEMS **Farm**

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T4.2: Assessing how policies enable or constrain the resilience of the arable farming in Saxony-Anhalt, Germany.

An application of the Resilience Assessment Tool (ResAT)

Work Performed by P12, Leibniz Institute of Agricultural Development in Transition Economies (IAMO)

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1 Identification of main farming system specific challenges

The Altmark is located in the German Federal State of Saxony-Anhalt (districts “Stendal” and “Altmarkkreis Salzwedel”), and captures important features of the large-scale agricultural structures of East German agriculture.

Fundamental for the region is the rather poor soil quality. This results in rather low yield levels in arable farming.

Socio-demographic challenges are the Outmigration and an aging population in rural areas, decreasing agricultural workforce and the risk of increasing labor scarcity for the agricultural sector, particularly in the livestock sector. Already now, the role of migrant workforce increases.

A specific issue is generational renewal in the management and ownership of large corporate farms. These farms have nowadays a high value, while current owners hardly benefited previously from dividends and the farms’ wealth.

Political challenges are the decreasing societal acceptance of large conventional farms and current production systems and the increasing risk of costly regulations. Also there are increasing debates on capping direct payments which could lead to distortions on the land market between labor extensive cash-crop farms and the more labor intensive corporate farms.

Market wise, there are increasing concerns that land sales and rental prices may become too high.

Other challenges will be the climate change, as soils are rather poor and average annual rainfall is rather low. So new extreme weather events will and possibly less annual rainfall may reduce productivity in the Altmark region.

On top of that, the Altmark region may be seen as more vulnerable as agricultural regions due to the rather weak capital base per hectare and the high share of rented land in rather large farms, the low proportion of high quality arable land, and the dominance of hired labor. I.e., the farms have a rather low share of equity capital, owned land and family labor. It is often argued that smaller farms are less vulnerable as they can tighten their belts in times of crises (e.g. low agricultural prices).

2 List of selected policy documents

<https://www.bmel.de/DE/Landwirtschaft/Agrarpolitik/Texte/GAP-NationaleUmsetzung.html>

https://www.bmel.de/DE/Laendliche-Raeume/03_Foerderung/Europa/texte/Foerderung2014-2020.html?nn=5774216¬First=true&docId=5493798

http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-13-937_en.htm

https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/food-farming-fisheries/by_country/documents/cap-in-your-country-de_en.pdf

https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/fileadmin/Bibliothek/Politik_und_Verwaltung/StK/Europa/ESI-Fonds-Neu_2017/Dokumente/ELER/EPLR/2018-02-27_Programme_2014DE06RDRP020_5_0_de.pdf

https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/sites/agriculture/files/policy-perspectives/policy-briefs/05_en.pdf

http://www.bmel.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/Broschueren/UmsetzungGAPinD.pdf?__blob=publicationFile

https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/sites/agriculture/files/future-of-cap/future_of_food_and_farming_communication_de.pdf

https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/rural-development-2014-2020_en

<https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/node/50>

<https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/esi-fonds-in-sachsen-anhalt/esi-fonds-in-sachsen-anhalt/>

https://mule.sachsen-anhalt.de/fileadmin/Bibliothek/Politik_und_Verwaltung/MLU/MLU/00_Aktuelles/1804/180418_Leitbild_Landwirtschaft_final_barrierefrei.pdf

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Eingehende Analyse

EINGEHENDE ANALYSE

EPRS - Wissenschaftlicher Dienst des Europäischen Parlaments

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Wissenschaftlicher Dienst für die Mitglieder

Dezember 2016 - PE 595.864

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3 Analysis

3.1 Table 5

Question	Scale (0 - 5)	Arguments
ROBUSTNESS		
<p>1a. To what extent is a focus on the short-term enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	4	<p>Unfortunately, there is little information available on short term goals. Thus, as many other policy goals, to a large share, short-term policy goals can only assessed indirectly.</p> <p>The focus of the German implementation of the CAP is on direct area payments. Only 4.5 % of the funds are transferred to the 2nd Pillar. Germany opted for redistributive payments for smaller farms instead of digressive payments for farms receiving more than 150 000 €. This can also be understood as support of existing farms without any obligations or perspectives affecting longer-term developments.</p> <p>The payments for young farmers in the 1st Pillar are also unconditional with exception of the requirement that the farmers are younger than 40 years. A business plan is not required.</p> <p>Greening requirements have been implemented in a way that only little adjustments are necessary to qualify.</p> <p>These measures which capture the bulk of payments indicate objectives which aim to support current farms in their current situation and to compensate them for (current) obligations they face, including environmental and animal standards.</p> <p>Accordingly, the bulk of support for the cap focusses on the following goals: (i) compensating and safeguarding the current services of the farming sector for society, (ii) compensating for current standards, (iii) safeguarding and stabilization of incomes of current farms (https://www.bmel.de/DE/Landwirtschaft/Agrarpolitik/_Texte/GAP-NationaleUmsetzung.html).</p> <p>Only 2nd pillar measures address medium and longer-term goals. The objectives of 2nd Pillar measures which are defined on the regional level are less short-term oriented (https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/fileadmin/Bibliothek/Politik_und_Verwaltung/StK/Europa/ESI-Fonds-Neu_2017/Dokumente/ELER/EPLR/2018-02-27_Programme_2014DE06RDRP020_5_0_de.pdf).</p>
<p>1b. To what extent is a focus on the short-term enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	4	<p>Area payments, redistributive support for small farms, young farmers' support and low requirements for greening activities which come at low costs for farmers enable business as usual for the short-term. (https://www.bmel.de/DE/Landwirtschaft/Agrarpolitik/_Texte/GAP-NationaleUmsetzung.html).</p> <p>The only exception are 2nd Pillar measures which suffer however from a relatively low budget.</p>

<p>2a. To what extent is protection of the status quo enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>The short-term goals as indicated in 1a correlate substantially with goals to protect the status quo, i.e. (i) compensating and safeguarding the (current) services of the farming sector for society, (ii) compensating for (current) standards, (iii) safeguarding and stabilization of incomes of current farms. The unconditional extra payments for the first 46 hectares can also be understood as support of the status quo. There are hardly any measures which support new entrants. The German Government heavily opposed the idea of "capping", arguing this to be inadequate for large Eastern German producer cooperatives and limited liabilities (GmbHs) which are often coined multi-family farms.</p>
<p>2b. To what extent is protection of the status quo enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	<p>5</p>	<p>The focus of policy instruments on direct area payments, „cheap“ greening requirements, first hectare payments, unconditional payments for farm successors, avoidance of "capping" (irrespective whether this would be a reasonable policy) help to preserve the status quo. In addition, the extra payments for less-favoured areas can be seen as instrument to protect the status quo not just of farms but also of the production structure as these are paid to large parts of the Germany in General and the German case-study region, the Altmark, in order to keep this land in agricultural use. In principle, only some 2nd Pillar measures have some long-term orientation.</p>
<p>3a. To what extent is the development of buffer resources enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>The direct area payments and redistributive payments aim among other reasons at safeguarding and stabilization of incomes of farms and thus are seen as means to provide buffer resources https://www.bmel.de/DE/Landwirtschaft/Agrarpolitik/Texte/GAP-NationaleUmsetzung.html).</p>
<p>3b. To what extent is the development of buffer resources enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>The direct area payments and redistributive payments stabilize incomes of farms and thus are seen as means to provide buffer resources. Also, the extra payments for less-favoured areas are additionally used as buffer resources besides the direct payments. Despite the fact, that substantial and increasing parts of these payments will be translated into higher land prices, farms benefit from increasing land values as they own some 20 to 35 % of the land. The crisis reserve can additionally be used as a buffer resource. If the market situation even worsens, those additional payments can be used to stabilise farm income.</p>
<p>4a. To what extent are other modes of managing risks enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	<p>3</p>	<p>German agriculture was over the past decades hardly affected by bankruptcies or insolvencies. A key strength is the relatively high and stable level of equity capital. Even many Eastern German farms raised equity capital over the past two decades substantially. The fact that Germany did not support risk insurances as part of the implementation of the CAP can be seen as an indicator that managing risks was not considered as a key task of policy but rather as entrepreneurial responsibility. However, interventions in the dairy sector (including payments for reduction of production) in 2016 and in response to the drought in 2018 indicate the objective to support farms in periods of crisis. Little attention is paid to other challenges, such as generational change. Payments for farm successors are unconditional. On the regional level, the state Saxony Anhalt invests a substantial share of its 2nd pillar measures in flood protection which does not support the</p>

		farms' risk management, but which has to be understood as sectoral risk management.
4b. To what extent are other modes of managing risks enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?	2	Policy instruments supporting risk management in a rather explicit way are not used with the exception of responses in periods of crises, such as the 2016 milk crisis and the 2018 drought and on the regional level flood protection. The latter, i.e. flood protection focusses to a substantial share on repair measures after the 2013 flood of the rivers Elbe and Saale.
ADAPTABILITY		
1a. To what extent is a focus on the middle-long term enabled or constrained by the policy goals?	4	Apart from the national focus on 1. Pillar measures, the ELER programming of the state Saxony Anhalt within the 2 nd Pillar focusses on objectives which address challenges for the middle-long term such as protection of agricultural resources (e.g., flood protection, access to labour forces, ...), access to innovations (including farms' access to broadband internet) and collaboration of science and business to develop innovations, public acceptance of livestock production, as well as strengthening the agricultural supply chain.
1b. To what extent is a focus on the middle-long term enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?	3	The implementation of measures for the middle-long term suffers partly from the limited budget as only 4.5 % of the 1 st pillar budget is transferred to the 2 nd Pillar. A second deficit is that quite some instruments can be rather seen as securing the current infrastructures than as investments in new infrastructures which allow for adaptations.
2a. To what extent is flexibility enabled or constrained by the policy goals?	4	In Germany First Pillar payments are fully decoupled to reduce market distortions. Moreover, Greening requirements allow flexible adjustments. Though these policy goals do not explicitly address flexibility, they indirectly allow farmers to respond in a very flexible way and without many (legal) requirements to a changing environment.
2b. To what extent is flexibility enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?	4	The strong decoupling relies on self-responsibly and market orientation of farmers and does not create high burdens for farms to adjust. Also the Greening requirements allow flexible responses. The same applies to certain 2 nd Pillar measures which support investments. However, there is no active support for measures which address flexibility.

<p>3a. To what extent are variety and tailor-made responses enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	<p>3</p>	<p>The German objective of supporting and implementing rather strong decoupling compared to other Member States creates low burdens for farmers and regional institutions to develop tailor-made responses. Whether this is an explicit policy goal is unclear. On the other hand, these objectives focus mainly on the current state and its protection which means at the same time that there is not much support for changes or for competing ideas and concepts. The soft implementation of support for small farmers allows that a very high variety of farm types can coexist in the different German regions with very large structural differences. This variety of farm types is however much smaller on the regional level. As the 2nd Pillar measures can be programmed on the state level, there is quite some room for tailor-made policies on the regional level to adapt to the regional issues.</p> <p>On the state level of Saxony Anhalt, the programming of the 2nd pillar explicitly addresses issues of diversity, including farm-level diversification, support of new entrees in a special young farmers program, strengthening the value chain, and engagement in the EIP.</p>
<p>3b. To what extent are variety and tailor-made responses enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	<p>3</p>	<p>The German support and implementation of rather strong decoupling compared to other Member States creates low burdens for farmers and regional institutions to develop tailor-made responses including activities for farm diversification. On the other hand, these measures focus mainly on the current state and its protection which means at the same time that there is little support for alternative ideas and concepts. The soft implementation of support for small farmers instead of more rigorous „capping“ measures allows that a very high variety of farm types can coexist. This variety of farm types is however much smaller on the regional level.</p> <p>On the state level of Saxony Anhalt, the programming of the 2nd pillar explicitly addresses issues of diversity, including farm-level diversification, support of new entrees in a special young farmers program (since 2017), strengthening the value chain, and engagement in the EIP.</p>
<p>4a. To what extent is social learning enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>LEADER tries to bring different agricultural and non-agricultural actors together. In focus groups the main goal is to work and learn together to achieve new views and strategies. Social learning is highly enabled by the LEADER tool.</p> <p>With the funding of cross-regional and transnational cooperation’s, different actors come together and can focus on working and learning together so that social learning is highly enabled.</p> <p>The implementation of EIP provides further opportunities for social learning and is used.</p> <p>With the help of Horizon 2020 academic projects where researchers and practitioners work together are funded in so called “multi actor projects”. Those possibly enhance learning processes which could help to learn new adaptability strategies for farmers in middle to long term perspective.</p> <p>The programming of ELER in the state of Saxony Anhalt explicitly addresses these goals.</p>
<p>4b. To what extent is social learning enabled or constrained by</p>	<p>2</p>	<p>As said before, several instruments, including LEADER, EIP, research collaborations provide opportunities for strengthening the links between agriculture, food production & forestry and research & innovation to support cooperation’s and therefore the social learning aspect. Actors can learn from each other and therefore a long term learning process can be implemented. Intensifying the cooperation between research and</p>

the policy instruments?		production creates social learning. These instruments are provided by the programming of ELER though the total budget is limited through the limited budget for the 2 nd Pillar. A key problem however seems to be that these measures are less adopted by the addressees as planned (https://www.km-bw.de/pb/site/pbs-bw-new/get/documents/MLR.LEL/PB5Documents/mlr/MEPL/mep1_extern/MEPL_Partnerschaftsvereinbarung/Fortschrittsbericht_2017-08-30_EB_SFC_Final_K01.pdf).
Transformation		
1a. To what extent is a focus on the long term enabled or constrained by the policy goals?	2	<p>There is little attention paid to long term issues and challenges. The three long-term CAP objectives viable food production, sustainable management of natural resources and climate action and balanced territorial development are not specific. Moreover, these very general objectives provide little guidance on which farms can work with the exception that farms can expect to receive 1st Pillar payments for a seven year period until 2020. As there is no indication for a fundamental policy change after 2020, it can be questioned whether there is no long-term strategy or whether there is a consciousness of a political path dependency which is used strategically.</p> <p>Additional support for small farms (first hectares payments) and payments for young farmers are unconditionally paid which indicate that there may be some vision that the status quo provides some long-term guideline though this seems to contradict the EU goal of fostering innovations.</p> <p>On the state level of Saxony-Anhalt, the recently established start-up aid for young farmers, support of EIPs and few further measures of the 2nd Pillar can be seen as indications of long-term goals. But these are just indications of long term goals.</p>
1b. To what extent is a focus on the long term enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?	2	<p>The 1st Pillar payments with a huge budget for guaranteed payments for a period of seven years starting in 2014 could be seen as a long term instrument in providing longer term planning safety to farmers. In principle, the planning safety declines year by year. However, at the same time these payments create some political path dependency in the sense that the next CAP reform may not change the system of direct payments dramatically. In this sense, farms can use these payments to some extent as security for financing long term investments. This argument may become particularly important if farms make longer term investment decisions such as land-rental contracts, land purchases which include a capitalization of direct payments.</p> <p>As direct payments are not committed to specific future challenges, this provokes the question whether there are longer term visions beyond the status quo or ensuring slow structural change.</p> <p>First hectare payments and support for young farmers may also create some path dependencies on the farm level having longer-term effects. Whether these longer-term effects or welfare increasing is doubtful. The Greening measures are hardly effective beyond good agri-environmental practices. Nevertheless, they may raise additional awareness of farmers for environmental challenges.</p> <p>Saxony-Anhalt established within the 2nd Pillar a new program providing start-up aids for young farmers. Whether this program with a limited budget can have longer-term effect may be questionable.</p>

<p>2a. To what extent is the dismantling of incentives that support the status quo enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>As addressed in Transformability 1a, there are strong indications that the current policy creates very likely path dependencies on the policy level as well as on the sectoral and farm level.</p> <p>The first hectare payments aim to support specifically small and medium-sized farms which represent the majority of farms. This policy can also be interpreted as an attempt to reduce structural changes. Very small farms can even benefit from a specific advantage of not being obliged in greening activities.</p> <p>Greening requirements have been reduced towards a minimum so that farmers have only low incentives to adapt production practices towards addressing the original intention of greening.</p> <p>The tool „Active farmers“ aims to close legal loopholes which have enabled a number of companies to claim direct payments even though they are not farmers in a traditional sense (e.g. airports, railway services, water works). But what if airports and railway services provide good and healthy grasslands, which are in perfect condition and support biodiversity? They are no farmers in a traditional sense, but they could contribute to a healthy agricultural land system which is sustainable and healthy. Thus, also the definition of „active farmers“ may rather be used to preserve the status quo of agriculture and may also be understood as a measure to avoid public criticism on direct payments.</p> <p>Only few measures within the 2nd Pillar provide opportunities to unlock problems of the status quo.</p>
<p>2b. To what extent is the dismantling of incentives that support the status quo enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	<p>2</p>	<p>In general, the current system of direct payments, support for small farms as well as the ineffective greening should rather be seen as measures which conserve previous and current incentives. Considering the addressed path dependency on the policy as well as the sectoral and farm level, the key argument in favor of the enormous amount of direct payments is the decoupling. I.e., farms can focus production on signals provided by markets and available technologies. In principle, also greening and 2nd Pillar measures can raise the farmers’ awareness for environmental and societal challenges.</p>
<p>3a. To what extent is in-depth learning enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	<p>2</p>	<p>The bulk of policy goals ignore in-depth learning as an issue. Only a small fraction of EU related goals and activities address this issue. Exceptions can be seen in certain policy instruments such as LEADER and EIP as well as H2020 projects. Within EIP and H2020, particularly public research institutes and universities follow the goal of in-depth understanding and learning. The institutes and universities address this new gained knowledge to politics and the farmers itself. Partly, the agricultural sector and the agribusiness are involved.</p> <p>Moreover, civil society organisations address these goals in relation to agricultural policy and agriculture. This is fostered by the awareness of the huge EU budget for CAP.</p> <p>On the other hand, the huge budget and its beneficiaries stimulate incentives to immunise against in-depth learning.</p> <p>In 2017, the Ministry of Environment, Agriculture and Energy of Saxony-Anhalt initiated the development of a mission statement (Leitbild - https://mule.sachsen-anhalt.de/fileadmin/Bibliothek/Politik_und_Verwaltung/MLU/MLU/00_Aktuelles/1804/180418_Leitbild_Landwirtschaft_final_barrierefrei.pdf).</p>

		<p>Involved were many institutions including farmers 'organisations, NGOs, researchers etc. In the end, the final paper was not supported by most farmers 'organisations. Apart from political reasons, the process was very much focussed on the defence of lobby interests and traditional perspectives on farming. Even though more than 80 % of the labour force in the regional farming business is hired labour, no representative of hired farm workers or local labour unions was involved.</p>
<p>3b. To what extent is in-depth learning enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	2	<p>The budget for the CAP stimulates public discourses. This occurs particularly before upcoming CAP reforms. In between the awareness is surprisingly low. Even the opportunity of Germany to increase the share of funds to be shifted from the 1st to the 2nd Pillar neither stimulated huge discussions. Eventually, there was little interest of NGOs. Eventually, existing lobby groups were able to immunise against a reform.</p> <p>The public consultation of the European Commission in 2017 lead to a substantial awareness and participation. However, it was quite framed towards current and popular visions, policies and policy objectives and left little room for in-depth learning.</p> <p>Here in Saxony-Anhalt, there are partnerships between different institutions as the Martin-Luther University Halle-Wittenberg (MLU), Landesanstalt für Landwirtschaft, Forsten und Gartenbau (LLFG), Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research (UFZ), Leibniz Institute of Agricultural Development in Transition Economies (IAMO), etc. with different locations all over Saxony-Anhalt. That creates a good network of institutions working on further innovations in the agricultural sector. This network enables resilience because of many different actors working on innovation to solve problems in the agricultural sector.</p> <p>Specific attention is paid to the bioeconomy and Saxony-Anhalt is supporting a research cluster Plant-based Bioeconomy with EFRE funds.</p>
<p>4a. To what extent is the enhancement and acceleration of niche innovations enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	3	<p>The European Innovation Partnerships are a new approach to research and innovation in the European Union. They help to pool expertise and bringing important stakeholders together so they can work as a group and find new innovations based on research in focus groups. The focus is clearly based on achieving faster and better results due to the new and highly connected cooperation's between researchers, farmers and innovation partners (e.g. lenders). Thus, EIP indicates the goal to encourage niche innovations.</p> <p>Also further activities within the 2nd pillar provide opportunities for niche innovations including innovations which address environmental challenges and societal interests, including marketing tools. A specific focus is on organic and partly also regional products and regional marketing.</p> <p>On the other hand, the budget for the relevant 2nd Pillar measures is not huge. Moreover, the uses of these funds compete with uses for current mainstream production. Both indicates goals which are rather complementary to the currently dominant types of production than to niches.</p>
<p>4b. To what extent is the enhancement and acceleration of</p>	4	<p>The EIP is enabling niche innovations as it is used as a bottom-up approach. Unfortunately, the budget is rather small.</p> <p>Beyond the EIP, policy instruments addressing niches within the 2nd Pillar focus on organic production and regional marketing. The focus is to a</p>

niche innovations enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?	<p>large extend on these niches themselves than on innovations within niches.</p> <p>On the other hand, there are little constraints to engage toward niche innovations. This is particularly supported by substantial and steady increases in research budgets on the federal as well as the state level over the past decade. Also collaboration between academic research, (agri-)business and civil society is increasingly supported and transfer activities of academic institutions are welcomed. Particular attention is paid to potentials of the bioeconomy.</p>
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3.2 Table 6

<i>Question: To what extent do the policy's goals and instruments enable or constrain the characteristics?</i>			
<i>Answers enabling</i>	<i>Answers constraining</i>	<i>Scores</i>	<i>Corresponding colour</i>
<i>Not clear</i>		<i>0</i>	
<i>Not enabling</i>	<i>Very constraining</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>Dark Red</i>
<i>Slightly enabling</i>	<i>Constraining</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>Dark Orange</i>
<i>Fairly enabling</i>	<i>Fairly constraining</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>Light Yellow</i>
<i>Enabling</i>	<i>Slightly constraining</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>Light Green</i>
<i>Very enabling</i>	<i>Not constraining</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>Dark Green</i>

3.3 ResAT-Wheel Policies

After visualising Table 5, one can clearly see differences between the resilience types in relation to the CAP policies. Robustness and Adaptability are fairly even scored. Both Robustness (short-term focus, protecting the status quo, buffer resources) and Adaptability (middle-term focus, flexibility, social learning) have three times the score four. Only the risk management, which counts to Robustness, has a score of 3 because risk insurance is not part of the implementation of the CAP in Germany. Also Variety, which counts to Adaptability, has only a score of three. Despite the fact, that the 2nd pillar in our survey region addresses diversity and diversification of farms, the German objectives of supporting and implementing focus mainly on the current state and its protection and therefore is fairly constraining for Variety. Noticeable is the mostly orange and red colour in the Transformability section. Because little attention is paid for the long-term goals (too imprecise) and therefore strong path dependencies exist which prevent Transformability.

3.4 ResAT-Wheel Instruments

Looking at the Robustness section, only the Risk management is scored fairly negative with a score of 2 because there is basically no risk insurance with exception of crisis support. The Adaptability Section is quite yellow-orange. Only Flexibility can score with a four. Middle-term focus and Variety is both scored with a three. The bullet points for that is the focusing on the current state and the

limited budget for the 2nd pillar. Social learning is scored with a two, partly because of the limited budget in the 2nd pillar. Also the addressees seem less adopting as planned. In contrast to that, the Transformability sector is mostly scored with a two. Because of declining long term planning ability of the farmers and political path dependencies, the long term focus is constrained by the current instruments. As mentioned before, current instruments rather preserve the status quo than dismantling them. Despite the fact of partnerships between research institutes and the University, the public awareness for the CAP is very small and therefore in-depth learning is mostly disabled. In contrast to that niche innovations are supported by EIP and instruments of the 2nd pillar. Therefore niche innovations are enabled by the policy instruments and are scored with a four.

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5 Annex

Table 3

Type of resilience	Key characteristics	Relevant texts for policy goals	Relevant texts for policy instruments
Robustness	1. Short term	The subsidies compensate for the fact that farmers in Europe, especially in the areas of environmental, animal and consumer protection, have to meet significantly higher standards than many of their colleagues in other parts of the world. These higher standards increase the cost of production in many cases and can be a competitive disadvantage in a globalized market. The promotion	<p>Basic premium: The redistribution of EU funds in favour of the new EU Member States will slightly reduce funds for Germany from 2014 to 2019. At the same time, premiums still varying regionally in Germany from initially 154 to 191 euros per hectare will be adjusted to around 175 euros per hectare by 2019.³ (BMEL, 2015)</p> <p>Small farmers: Business start-up aid up to 15,000 euros per small farm.⁴ (EC, 2013, p. 7)</p>

³ <https://www.bmel.de/DE/Landwirtschaft/Agrarpolitik/Texte/GAP-NationaleUmsetzung.html>

„Basisprämie: Durch die Umverteilung der EU-Mittel zugunsten der neuen EU-Mitgliedstaaten werden sich die Mittel für Deutschland 2014 bis 2019 geringfügig verringern. Parallel dazu werden die regional in Deutschland noch unterschiedlichen Prämien von zunächst 154 bis 191 Euro pro Hektar bis 2019 auf rund 175 Euro pro Hektar angeglichen.“

⁴ [http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release MEMO-13-937_en.htm](http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-13-937_en.htm)

		should compensate for this disadvantage and ensures high product safety and quality. ² (BMEL, 2015)	
	2. Protecting the status quo	German government papers address the following goals: (i) compensating and safeguarding the current services of the farming sector for society, (ii) compensating for current standards, (iii) safeguarding and stabilization of incomes of current farms. ⁵ The objectives of 2 nd Pillar measures which are defined on the regional level are less short-term oriented. ⁶ habitats.	In order to give a boost to small/medium-sized farms, the German authorities are using 7 % of the national envelope for the so-called redistributive payment , providing a top-up payment for all beneficiaries of 50 euros/ha for their first 30 hectares and 30 euros/ha for every subsequent hectare up to 46 hectares. The smallest-sized farms will benefit from a flat-rate simplified system of support (the Small Farmers Scheme), with a maximum of 1250 euros per farm. ⁷ (EC,2016,p.2) An annual donation of from 150 up to 200 euros per livestock unit. ⁸ Improvement of Agricultural Structure and Coastal Protection The duration of the obligations of agro-environmental and climate measures is 5 years. An annual extension up to two years is possible. ⁹ Greening options allows for many rather cheap adaptations of farmers which have little effect. ¹⁰
	3. Buffer resources	Direct payments contribute to farmers' income security and income stabilization by cushioning the impact of sometimes extreme price	Crisis reserve: A crisis reserve will be created every year for an amount of 400 million euros (in 2011 prices) by application of financial discipline. If the amount is not used for a crisis it will be

² <https://www.bmel.de/DE/Landwirtschaft/Agrarpolitik/Texte/GAP-NationaleUmsetzung.html>

„Die Förderungen sind ein Ausgleich dafür, dass Landwirte in Europa gerade in den Bereichen Umwelt-, Tier- und Verbraucherschutz deutlich höhere Standards einhalten müssen als viele ihrer Kollegen in anderen Teilen der Welt. Diese höheren Standards verteuern in vielen Fällen die Produktion und können in einem globalisierten Markt als Wettbewerbsnachteil wirken. Die Förderung soll diesen Nachteil ausgleichen und sorgt für eine hohe Produktsicherheit und Qualität.“

⁵ <https://www.bmel.de/DE/Landwirtschaft/Agrarpolitik/Texte/GAP-NationaleUmsetzung.html>

⁶ https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/fileadmin/Bibliothek/Politik_und_Verwaltung/StK/Europa/ESI-Fonds-Neu_2017/Dokumente/ELER/EPLR/2018-02-27_Programme_2014DE06RDRP020_5_0_de.pdf

⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/food-farming-fisheries/by_country/documents/cap-in-your-country-de_en.pdf

⁸ <http://www.landesrecht.sachsen-anhalt.de/jportal/?quelle=jlink&query=VVST-782400-MLU-20150916-SF&psml=bssahprod.psml&max=true>

⁹ https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/fileadmin/Bibliothek/Politik_und_Verwaltung/StK/Europa/ESI-Fonds-Neu_2017/Dokumente/ELER/EPLR/2018-02-27_Programme_2014DE06RDRP020_5_0_de.pdf (p. 286)

¹⁰ https://en.nabu.de/imperia/md/content/nabude/landwirtschaft/agrarreform/171121-peer_et_al_2017_cap_fitness_check.pdf

		<p>fluctuations on agricultural products.¹¹ (BMEL, 2015)</p> <p>Compensation supplement for less-favoured areas → securing local land management in less-favoured areas; Continuation of agricultural employment; Preservation of the rural habitat¹²</p>	<p>reimbursed to farmers as direct payments in the following year.¹³ (EC,2013,p.8)</p> <p>At least 30 euros / ha up to 110 euros / ha per year. Allocation is degressive¹⁴.</p>
	4. Other risk management measures	<p>Moreover, new safeguard clauses are introduced for all sectors to enable the Commission to take emergency measures to respond to general market disturbances.¹⁵ (EC,2013,p.5)</p> <p>Reconstruction of agricultural production potential damaged by natural disasters and introduction of appropriate preventive measures Support for investment in preventive measures for reduction of the consequences of probable natural disasters, adverse climatic events and catastrophic events. The support of risk management of agricultural</p>	<p>These measures will be funded from a Crisis Reserve financed by annually reducing direct payments. Funds not used for crisis measures will be returned to farmers in the following year. In case of severe imbalance in the market, the Commission may also authorize producer organizations or inter branch organizations, respecting specific safeguards, to take certain temporary measures collectively (for example market withdrawal or storage by private operators) to stabilize the sector concerned.¹⁹ (EC,2013,p.5)</p> <p>In addition, the second pillar offers a new risk-management toolkit including insurance schemes for crops, animals and plants, as well as mutual funds and an income stabilization tool.²⁰ (EC,2013,p.6)</p>

¹¹ <https://www.bmel.de/DE/Landwirtschaft/Agrarpolitik/Texte/GAP-NationaleUmsetzung.html>

„Die Direktzahlungen tragen zur Einkommenssicherung und Einkommensstabilisierung der Landwirte bei, indem sie die Auswirkungen der zum Teil extremen Preisschwankungen bei Agrarprodukten abfedern.“

¹² <https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/esi-fonds-in-sachsen-anhalt/ueber-die-europaeischen-struktur-und-investitionsfonds/eler/eplr/eler-massnahmen-im-ueberblick/tier-und-flaechenbezogene-massnahmen/ausgleichszulage-fuer-benachteiligte-gebiete/>

¹³ [http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release MEMO-13-937 en.htm](http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-13-937_en.htm)

¹⁴ <https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/esi-fonds-in-sachsen-anhalt/ueber-die-europaeischen-struktur-und-investitionsfonds/eler/eplr/eler-massnahmen-im-ueberblick/tier-und-flaechenbezogene-massnahmen/ausgleichszulage-fuer-benachteiligte-gebiete/>

¹⁵ [http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release MEMO-13-937 en.htm](http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release MEMO-13-937_en.htm)

¹⁹ [http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release MEMO-13-937 en.htm](http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release MEMO-13-937_en.htm)

²⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/sites/agriculture/files/policy-perspectives/policy-briefs/05_en.pdf

		<p>holdings under the rural development programs aims to reduce natural risks and potential damage. In addition, there are positive contributions to the protection of agricultural production potential through the implementation of support measures in accordance with Art. 17 (in particular land reclamation procedure with focus on erosion control). Economic instruments to hedge operational risks (special insurance, funds up Reciprocity, income stabilization instruments acc. Art. 35 et seq. VO (EU) 1305/2013) are not prioritized.</p> <p>Erosion protection The goal is the prevention of weather-related events with significant soil erosion for vulnerable sites and dealing with the consequences of such events. According to the concept, this should lead to erosion protection for rural Saxony-Anhalt with the implementation of risk analyses, the preparation of management plans, the development of solution approaches, the information and awareness of the actors and the support for implementation through specialized law, planning and funding instruments.¹⁶</p>	<p>Reconstruction of agricultural production potential damaged by natural disasters and introduction of appropriate preventive measures European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD): 90.000.000 euros National co-financing: 30.000.000</p> <p>Erosion protection</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk analyses • Preparation of management plans • Information and awareness of actors • Specialized law, planning and funding instruments²¹ <p>Less favoured areas With using the applied indicators</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yield indicator as an indicator of “normal soil productivity” and • Mounted portion of winter wheat on arable land <p>394 territorial units with 257,786 ha are excluded from the first stage. In result there will be 302 districts classified as areas with disadvantages. Together, they have an agricultural area of 200,526 ha.²²</p>
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¹⁶ https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/fileadmin/Bibliothek/Politik_und_Verwaltung/StK/Europa/ESI-Fonds-Neu_2017/Dokumente/ELER/EPLR/2018-02-27_Programme_2014DE06RDRP020_5_0_de.pdf

²¹ https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/fileadmin/Bibliothek/Politik_und_Verwaltung/StK/Europa/ESI-Fonds-Neu_2017/Dokumente/ELER/EPLR/2018-02-27_Programme_2014DE06RDRP020_5_0_de.pdf

²² https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/fileadmin/Bibliothek/Politik_und_Verwaltung/StK/Europa/ESI-Fonds-Neu_2017/Dokumente/ELER/EPLR/2018-02-27_Programme_2014DE06RDRP020_5_0_de.pdf (p. 15)

		<p>Measures against animal diseases Guidelines on the structure and functioning of crisis centres.¹⁷</p> <p>Payments for area with disadvantages because of natural or other specific reasons The newly setting “Disadvantaged Agricultural Zone” represents the natural disadvantages for farms in Saxony-Anhalt in a realistic form. It essentially coincides with the many years of experience of agricultural practice in the management of less favoured areas in Saxony-Anhalt. The expulsion shows that the less favoured areas are in the north (Altmark), the southwest, northwest and west of the country.¹⁸</p>	
Adaptability	1. Middle-long term	<p>It represents another milestone in the CAP's history placing the joint provision of public and private goods at the core of policy. Farmers should be rewarded for the services they deliver to the wider public, such as landscapes, farmland biodiversity, climate stability even though they have no market value.²³ (EC,2013,p.5)</p> <p>The ELER programming of the state Saxony Anhalt within the 2nd Pillar focusses on objectives which address</p>	<p>Therefore, a new policy instrument of the first pillar (greening) is directed to the provision of environmental public goods, which constitutes a major change in the policy framework.²⁶ (EC,2013,p.5)</p> <p>Other changes introduced in the 2013 CAP a new 25 % aid supplement for young farmers for the first 5 years.²⁷ (EC,2016,p.2)</p> <p>During the first two years: 403 euros / ha farmland / grassland 1,215 euros / ha vegetables 1,657 euros / ha permanent crops In the following years: 273 euros / ha farmland / grassland</p>

¹⁷ https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/fileadmin/Bibliothek/Politik_und_Verwaltung/StK/Europa/ESI-Fonds-Neu_2017/Dokumente/ELER/EPLR/2018-02-27_Programme_2014DE06RDRP020_5_0_de.pdf

¹⁸ https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/fileadmin/Bibliothek/Politik_und_Verwaltung/StK/Europa/ESI-Fonds-Neu_2017/Dokumente/ELER/EPLR/2018-02-27_Programme_2014DE06RDRP020_5_0_de.pdf (p.15)

²³ https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/sites/agriculture/files/policy-perspectives/policy-briefs/05_en.pdf

²⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/sites/agriculture/files/policy-perspectives/policy-briefs/05_en.pdf

²⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/food-farming-fisheries/by_country/documents/cap-in-your-country-de_en.pdf

		<p>challenges for the middle-long term such as protection of agricultural resources (e.g., flood protection, access to labour forces, ...), access to innovations (including farms' access to broadband internet) and collaboration of science and business to develop innovations, public acceptance of livestock production, as well as strengthening the agricultural supply chain.²⁴</p> <p>Further issues include: Introduction of organic farming practices throughout the farm to have sustainable improvement of natural and economic production conditions that are compatible with environmental concerns and the preservation of natural habitat, reduction of nitrate intake in the soil, avoidance of short crops rotation, conservation / improvement of biodiversity in the agricultural landscape.²⁵ (MULE, 2018)</p>	<p>468 euros / ha vegetables 975 euros / ha permanent crops²⁸</p> <p>ELER measures address to quite some extent the protection of agricultural resources (e.g., flood protection, access to labour forces, ...), access to innovations (including farms' access to broadband internet) and collaboration of science and business to develop innovations, public acceptance of livestock production, as well as strengthening the agricultural supply chain.²⁹</p>
	2. Flexibility	There is new flexibility for Member States in the budgeting and implementation of first Pillar instruments, acknowledging the wide diversity of agriculture, agronomic production potential and climatic, environmental as	Member States also have the right to use a redistributive payment for the first hectares whereby they can take up to 30% of the national envelope and redistribute it to farmers on their first 30 hectares (or up to the average farm size in a Member State if higher than 30ha). This will have a

²⁴ https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/fileadmin/Bibliothek/Politik_und_Verwaltung/StK/Europa/ESI-Fonds-Neu_2017/Dokumente/ELER/EPLR/2018-02-27_Programme_2014DE06RDRP020_5_0_de.pdf

²⁵ <https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/esi-fonds-in-sachsen-anhalt/ueber-die-europaeischen-struktur-und-investitionsfonds/eler/eplr/eler-massnahmen-im-ueberblick/tier-und-flaechenbezogene-massnahmen/msl/oekologischer-biologischer-landbau/>

²⁸ <https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/esi-fonds-in-sachsen-anhalt/ueber-die-europaeischen-struktur-und-investitionsfonds/eler/eplr/eler-massnahmen-im-ueberblick/tier-und-flaechenbezogene-massnahmen/msl/oekologischer-biologischer-landbau/>

²⁹ https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/fileadmin/Bibliothek/Politik_und_Verwaltung/StK/Europa/ESI-Fonds-Neu_2017/Dokumente/ELER/EPLR/2018-02-27_Programme_2014DE06RDRP020_5_0_de.pdf

		<p>well as socio-economic conditions and needs across the EU.³⁰ (EC,2013,p.5)</p> <p>Measures to simplify program implementation As part of programming, a cross-fund strategy has been developed in order to use flexibility within and between funds and achieve synergy effects, and thus to use conveying equipment with the greatest possible efficiency.³¹</p>	<p>significant redistributive effect.³² (EC, 2013, p.2)</p> <p>Germany uses the option offered in EU law to restack some funding's between the two pillars of the GAP. The Direct Payments Implementation Act provides that in the period 2015-2019 4,5% of the funds of the annual national ceiling for direct payments will be restacked to the second pillar (rural Development)³³ (BMEL,2015,p.12-13)</p> <p>Measured to simplify program implementation For the development of the strategy for the use of the funds, the definition and demarcation of the tasks between the funds and the definition of objectives, a cross-fund analysis of the initial situation (socio-economic analyses) and SWOT analysis are implemented.³⁴</p>
	<p>3. Variety and tailor made responses</p>	<p>Start-up aid for young farmers “If someone sees their future in rural areas and wants to start their own business, we support this financially with 70,000 euros for a period of five years.” “This program is open to all start-ups, to ecologically and conventionally-managed businesses. It has been my experience that the young generation attaches great importance to the interests of the environment, nature and society. I am sure that we will pave the way for responsible young people</p>	<p>Start-up aid for young farmers Within 24 months of setting up a business, applications can be made in this program if the young farmer is younger than 40 years old. 70,000 euros will be paid out for a period of five years. This jump-start is connected with the demand that services be provided for ecological sustainability and resource efficiency.³⁸</p> <p>This shall be funded by up to 2% of the national envelope and will be compulsory for all Member states.³⁹ (EC,2013,p.2)</p> <p>Between 10% and 40% of the eligible expenditure Minimum investment volume: 20,000 euros</p>

³⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/sites/agriculture/files/policy-perspectives/policy-briefs/05_en.pdf

³¹ https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/fileadmin/Bibliothek/Politik_und_Verwaltung/StK/Europa/ESI-Fonds-Neu_2017/Dokumente/ELER/EPLR/2018-02-27_Programme_2014DE06RDRP020_5_0_de.pdf

³² http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-13-937_en.htm

³³ http://www.bmel.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/Broschueren/UmsetzungGAPinD.pdf?__blob=publicationFile

³⁴ https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/fileadmin/Bibliothek/Politik_und_Verwaltung/StK/Europa/ESI-Fonds-Neu_2017/Dokumente/ELER/EPLR/2018-02-27_Programme_2014DE06RDRP020_5_0_de.pdf

³⁸ https://mule.sachsen-anhalt.de/newsarchiv/artikel-detail/?tx_news_pi1%5Bnews%5D=6606&tx_news_pi1%5Bcontroller%5D=News&tx_news_pi1%5Baction%5D=detail&cHash=9f921f5e641138f5fb3e066d368d8101

³⁹ http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-13-937_en.htm

		<p>here. Equipped with the latest knowledge, they will be an asset to both the industry and the villages where they settle.” “I am happy about every young farmer, who has the courage and a vision of the future to become self-employed. Because in agriculture there will be a generational change in the next few years.”³⁵</p> <p>On top of the Basic Payment (see chart 4), the green direct payment and possible additional support for Areas facing Natural or other specific Constraints will contribute to specific environmental and territorial objectives.³⁶ <i>(EC,2013,p.7)</i></p> <p>Agricultural investment promotion program: Improvement of production and working conditions of farms; Rationalization and reduction of production costs; Increase of operational value; Improvement of consumer, animal, environmental and climate protection → Construction, acquisition or modernization of immovable property; Purchase of new machines and equipment of the interior, including computer software; Architectural and</p>	<p>Upper funding limit: 2 million euros, which can only be used once in 2014-2020⁴⁰</p>
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³⁵ https://mule.sachsen-anhalt.de/newsarchiv/artikel-detail/?tx_news_pi1%5Bnews%5D=6606&tx_news_pi1%5Bcontroller%5D=News&tx_news_pi1%5Baction%5D=detail&cHash=9f921f5e641138f5fb3e066d368d8101 (06.2017, Prof. Dr. Dalbert, Agriculture minister of Saxony-Anhalt)

³⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/sites/agriculture/files/policy-perspectives/policy-briefs/05_en.pdf

⁴⁰ <https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/esi-fonds-in-sachsen-anhalt/ueber-die-europaeischen-struktur-und-investitionsfonds/eler/eplr/eler-massnahmen-im-ueberblick/investitionen-in-die-landwirtschaft/agrarinvestitionsfoerderungprogramm/>

		<p>engineering services, building permits, consultancy, supervision of construction investments, feasibility studies, acquisition of patent rights and licenses; Supervision of investment projects with eligible building investment volume of more than 100,000 euros³⁷</p>	
	4. Social learning	<p>Not only is the use of technologies, but also access to well-founded, relevant and new knowledge very unevenly distributed in the European Union. Thereby the performance of certain CAP instruments and the general competitiveness and the development potential of the agricultural sector are limited. On the other hand, the CAP allows for an improved flow of information between partners from different parts of the EU, which brings a significant added value. This saves costs, uses EU funds more effectively and boosts innovation in the different parts of the EU.⁴¹ <i>(EC,2017,p.14)</i></p> <p>Preparation / initiation of cooperation's (cross-regional, transnational)</p>	<p>Strengthening links between agriculture, food production and forestry, and research and innovation: Support for cooperation's to strengthen the integration of the agricultural and forestry business sector in research, development and innovation activities with the aim of initiating product/process developments Strengthening the incentives for research institutions to carry out research, development and innovation projects with companies in order to make use of the potential of applied research Intensify cooperation between research, production and processing/marketing⁴⁴ <i>(ISW,2013,p.69)</i></p> <p>Preparation / initiation of cooperation's (area spreading, transnational) Amount of promotion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public and non-profit bodies: up to 90% of eligible expenditure • Other applicants under private law: up to 80% of the eligible expenditure

³⁷ <https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/esi-fonds-in-sachsen-anhalt/ueber-die-europaeischen-struktur-und-investitionsfonds/eler/eplr/eler-massnahmen-im-ueberblick/investitionen-in-die-landwirtschaft/agrarinvestitionsfoerderprogramm/>

⁴¹ https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/sites/agriculture/files/future-of-cap/future_of_food_and_farming_communication_de.pdf

„Nicht nur der Einsatz von Technologien, sondern auch der Zugang zu fundiertem, relevantem und neuem Wissen ist in der Union sehr ungleich verteilt. Dadurch werden die Leistung bestimmter GAP-Instrumente sowie die allgemeine Wettbewerbsfähigkeit und das Entwicklungspotenzial des Agrarsektors eingeschränkt. Andererseits dazu ermöglicht die GAP einen verbesserten Informationsfluss zwischen Partnern aus verschiedenen Teilen der EU, was einen erheblichen Mehrwert bringt, da hierdurch Kosten gespart, EU-Mittel wirksamer eingesetzt und Innovationen in den verschiedenen Teilen der EU beschleunigt werden.“

⁴⁴ https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/fileadmin/Bibliothek/Politik_und_Verwaltung/StK/Europa/ELER/2013_07_29_Entwurf_EPLR_LSA.pdf

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spending on the initiation of transnational or cross regional cooperation • Project management will be founded up to 20% of the grant⁴² <p>Management and awareness-raising in the context of local development strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A) Support of local action groups (LAG) • B) Raising public awareness of measures related to the implementation of LEADER development strategies⁴³ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A maximum of 3,500 euros for cross-regional initiation and a maximum of 8,000 euros for transnational initiation⁴⁵ <p>Management and awareness-raising in the context of local development strategies</p> <p>What is being funded?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expenditure related to the management of local action groups (personal expenses, operational expenses, material expenses, proper expenditure) • Expenditure on awareness raising of the population <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Public relation (Website, publications...) ○ Training of LAG members and other interested citizens ○ Travel expenses for LAG chairmen and their deputies for travel by public transport ○ Membership fees in the LEADER network • Amount of promotion <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ A) Up to 90% of eligible expenditure; Upper limit 100,000 euros per LAG or 170,000 euros for several LAGs, if awarded to a company ○ B) Up to 90% of eligible expenditure; Upper limit 20,000 euros per LAG <p>Overall, this support may not exceed 25% pf the total public expenditure incurred in</p>
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⁴² <https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/esi-fonds-in-sachsen-anhalt/ueber-die-europaeischen-struktur-und-investitionsfonds/eler/eplr/eler-massnahmen-im-ueberblick/unterstuetzung-der-lokalen-entwicklung-leaderclld/vorbereitunganbahnung-von-kooperationen-gebietsuebergreifend-transnational/>

⁴³ <https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/esi-fonds-in-sachsen-anhalt/ueber-die-europaeischen-struktur-und-investitionsfonds/eler/eplr/eler-massnahmen-im-ueberblick/unterstuetzung-der-lokalen-entwicklung-leaderclld/management-und-sensibilisierung-im-zusammenhang-mit-lokalen-entwicklungsstrategien/>

⁴⁵ <https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/esi-fonds-in-sachsen-anhalt/ueber-die-europaeischen-struktur-und-investitionsfonds/eler/eplr/eler-massnahmen-im-ueberblick/unterstuetzung-der-lokalen-entwicklung-leaderclld/vorbereitunganbahnung-von-kooperationen-gebietsuebergreifend-transnational/>

			<p>the implementation of all LEADER development strategies.⁴⁶</p> <p>A key problem however seems to be that these measures are less adopted by the addressees as planned.⁴⁷</p> <p>○</p>
Transformability	1. Long term	<p>Since the role of the CAP is to provide a policy framework that supports and encourages producers to address these challenges while remaining coherent with other EU policies, this translates into three long-term CAP objectives: viable food production, sustainable management of natural resources and climate action and balanced territorial development.⁴⁸ (EC,2013,p.2)</p> <p>Land Consolidation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reorganization of rural land ownership • Improvement of the agricultural structure • Preservation and development of an efficient nature budget⁴⁹ <p>Start-up aid for young farmers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualified farmers should be given 	<p>The EU's rural development policy is funded through the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) worth 100 billion euros from 2014-2020, with each EU country receiving a financial allocation for the 7-year period. This will leverage a further 61 billion euros of public funding in the Member States.⁵² (EC,2016)</p> <p>From 2014 – 2020 Germany has 8.3 billion euros of EU funds from the EAFRD.⁵³ (BMEL, 2015,p.84)</p> <p>Land Consolidation: from 75% up to 100% of the eligible expenses will be supported⁵⁴</p> <p>Start-up aid for young farmers: The funding is 70,000 euros. For the first two years 35,000 euros, for the third and fourth year 21,000 euros and for the fifth year of the existence founding 14,000 euros.⁵⁵</p>

⁴⁶ <https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/esi-fonds-in-sachsen-anhalt/ueber-die-europaeischen-struktur-und-investitionsfonds/eler/eplr/eler-massnahmen-im-ueberblick/unterstuetzung-der-lokalen-entwicklung-leaderclld/management-und-sensibilisierung-im-zusammenhang-mit-lokalen-entwicklungsstrategien/>

⁴⁷ https://www.km-bw.de/pb/site/pbs-bw-new/get/documents/MLR.LEL/PB5Documents/mlr/MEPL/mepl_extern/MEPL_Partnerschaftsvereinbarung/Fortschrittsbericht_2017-08-30_EB_SFC_Final_K01.pdf

⁴⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/sites/agriculture/files/policy-perspectives/policy-briefs/05_en.pdf

⁴⁹ <https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/esi-fonds-in-sachsen-anhalt/ueber-die-europaeischen-struktur-und-investitionsfonds/eler/eplr/eler-massnahmen-im-ueberblick/investitionen-in-die-landwirtschaft/flurneuordnung/>

⁵² https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/rural-development-2014-2020_en

⁵³ http://www.bmel.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/Broschueren/UmsetzungGAPinD.pdf?__blob=publicationFile

⁵⁴ <https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/esi-fonds-in-sachsen-anhalt/ueber-die-europaeischen-struktur-und-investitionsfonds/eler/eplr/eler-massnahmen-im-ueberblick/investitionen-in-die-landwirtschaft/flurneuordnung/>

⁵⁵ <https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/esi-fonds-in-sachsen-anhalt/ueber-die-europaeischen-struktur-und-investitionsfonds/eler/eplr/eler-massnahmen-im-ueberblick/investitionen-in-die-landwirtschaft/existenzgruendungsbeihilfe-fuer-junglandwirte/>

		<p>easier access to the agricultural sector</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The generation change should be supported • Sustainable business start-ups that are establishing themselves in the region⁵⁰ <p>Improving the economic performance of all farms, supporting the operational restructuring and modernization, in particular with a view to increasing market participation and orientation as well as agricultural diversification. With the support, at least 8 percent of agricultural companies in Saxony-Anhalt should invest in operationally significant development projects.⁵¹</p>	
	2. Dismantling incentives that support the status quo	<p>“Active farmers”: In order to iron out a number of legal loopholes which have enabled a limited number of companies to claim Direct Payments, even though their primary business activity is not agricultural, the reform tightens the rule on active farmers.⁵⁶ (EC,2013,p.4)</p> <p>Compensation payments under Natura 2000 (Avoidance of fertilizers)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ban or restriction on fertilization on grassland 	<p>A new negative list of professional business activities which should be excluded from receiving Direct Payments (covering airports, railway services, water works, real estate services and permanent sports & recreation grounds) will be mandatory for Member States, unless the individual businesses concerned can show that they have genuine farming activity. Member States will be able to extend the negative list to include further business activities.⁵⁷ (EC,2013,p.4)</p> <p>Compensation payments under Natura 2000 (Avoidance of fertilizers)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ban on fertilization on grassland: > 1,5 roughage consuming animal unit (RCAUs) / ha 200 euros / ha

⁵⁰ <https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/esi-fonds-in-sachsen-anhalt/ueber-die-europaeischen-struktur-und-investitionsfonds/eler/eplr/eler-massnahmen-im-ueberblick/investitionen-in-die-landwirtschaft/existenzgruendungsbeihilfe-fuer-junglandwirte/>

⁵¹ https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/fileadmin/Bibliothek/Politik_und_Verwaltung/StK/Europa/ESI-Fonds-Neu_2017/Dokumente/ELER/EPLR/2018-02-27_Programme_2014DE06RDRP020_5_0_de.pdf (p. 102)

⁵⁶ http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-13-937_en.htm

⁵⁷ http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-13-937_en.htm

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stabilize agricultural production by offsetting costs and income losses caused by farming restrictions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Restriction of fertilization on grassland >1,5 RCAUs / ha 175 euros / ha⁵⁸
	3. In-depth learning	<p>LEADER: Greater emphasis on awareness-raising and other preparatory support for strategies; promoting flexibility for operating with other funds in local areas, i.e. rural-urban co-operation; N.B. LEADER will now be used as the common approach for community-led local development by the following European Structural and Investment Funds (ESI): the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), European Social Fund (ESF), European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF) and the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development EAFRD).⁵⁹ (EC,2013,p.7)</p> <p>Implementation of measures in the context of local development strategies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To test and apply new opportunities for sustainable rural development Reduction of emigration and establishment of a welcome culture 	<p>Promoting lifelong learning and vocational training in agriculture and forestry. Support for the activities of young professionals (especially the Initial training) in agriculture and forestry Support for lifelong learning activities of agricultural and forestry workers and managers⁶¹ (ISW,2013,p.69)</p> <p>Implementation of measures in the context of local development strategies: Amount of promotion:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public corporations: up to 80% of eligible expenditure max. 350,000 euros Non-profit corporations and recognized religious communities: up to 75% of eligible expenditure max. 350,000 euros Other applicants under private law: up to 50% of eligible expenditure max. 50,000 euros

⁵⁸ <https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/esi-fonds-in-sachsen-anhalt/ueber-die-europaeischen-struktur-und-investitionsfonds/eler/eplr/eler-massnahmen-im-ueberblick/naturschutzmassnahmen/ausgleichszahlungen-im-rahmen-von-natura-2000-bereich-landwirtschaft/>

⁵⁹ [http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release MEMO-13-937 en.htm](http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-13-937_en.htm)

⁶¹ https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/fileadmin/Bibliothek/Politik_und_Verwaltung/StK/Europa/ELER/2013_07_29_Entwurf_EPLR_LSA.pdf

„Förderung des lebenslangen Lernens und der beruflichen Bildung in der Land- und Forstwirtschaft

- Unterstützung von Aktivitäten der beruflichen Nachwuchsgewinnung (insbes. Erstausbildung) in der Land- und Forstwirtschaft
- Unterstützung von Aktivitäten des Lebenslangen Lernens von Beschäftigten und Führungskräften der Land- und Forstwirtschaft“

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion of intercultural initiatives as well as cultural and tourist infrastructures • Improvement and deepening of urban-rural relations • Increase knowledge transfer in rural areas • Accompanying demographic change to maintain the quality of life in rural areas⁶⁰ 	
	4. Enhancing and accelerating niche innovations	<p>Five European Innovation Partnerships (EIP) have been launched in the context of the Innovation Union. European Innovation Partnerships are a new approach to research and innovation. EIPs help to pool expertise and resources by bringing together public and private sectors at EU, national and regional levels, combining supply and demand side measures. All EIPs focus on societal benefits and fast modernization. They support the cooperation between research and innovation partners so that they are able to achieve better and faster results compared to existing approaches.⁶²</p> <p>Cross-territorial cooperation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extension of local perspectives • Promoting knowledge transfer, 	<p>In the state of Saxony-Anhalt there are extensive research and innovation potentials related to the agricultural sector. These include in particular departments and institutes at the University of Anhalt and the Martin-Luther-Universität in Halle, the Regional Institute for Agriculture, Forestry and horticulture of the state of Saxony-Anhalt (LLFG) as well as institutes of the Helmholtz and Leibniz-Gemeinschaft with locations in Magdeburg, Bad Lauchstädt, Falkenberg, Halle and Gatersleben. In addition, technology-oriented networks exist in the field of life science as well as in the field of renewable energy. The density, efficiency and networking of the existing facilities provide a very good starting point for supporting innovation processes in the agricultural sector.⁶⁴ (ISW,2013,p.38)</p> <p>Cross-territorial cooperation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spending on the implementation of territorial cooperation projects • Project management up to 20% of the grant • Public and non-profit bodies: up to 90% of eligible expenditure

⁶⁰ <https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/esi-fonds-in-sachsen-anhalt/ueber-die-europaeischen-struktur-und-investitionsfonds/eler/eplr/eler-massnahmen-im-ueberblick/unterstuetzung-der-lokalen-entwicklung-leaderclld/umsetzung-von-massnahmen-im-rahmen-der-lokalen-entwicklungsstrategien/>

⁶² <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/node/50>

⁶⁴ https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/fileadmin/Bibliothek/Politik_und_Verwaltung/StK/Europa/ELER/2013_07_29_Entwurf_EPLR_LSA.pdf

		<p>innovation or the competitiveness of the sub-region⁶³</p> <p>Nationwide expansion of high-performance broadband infrastructure Promoting access to Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), its usage and quality in rural areas. The current coverage rate with broadband connections greater than 50 Mbps is at only 19.2 percent in Saxony-Anhalt, spreading over a few areas in large cities. The rural area can be considered in its entirety with a supply rate of 5.8 percent as a “white spot”. The expansion of high-performance broadband is a necessity when looking at the context of equal living conditions (see SWOT analysis)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other applicants under private law: up to 80% of the eligible expenditure • A maximum of 50,000 euros in cross-territorial cooperation, exceptionally 70,000 euros in cross-national cooperation, provided that a LAG (local action groups) from Saxony-Unhalt takes the lead⁶⁵ <p>Nationwide expansion of high-performance broadband infrastructure By 2020, Saxony-Anhalt will have broadband connections of the next generation (NGA) with at least 50 Mbps available.</p>
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⁶³ <https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/esi-fonds-in-sachsen-anhalt/ueber-die-europaeischen-struktur-und-investitionsfonds/eler/eplr/eler-massnahmen-im-ueberblick/unterstuetzung-der-lokalen-entwicklung-leaderclld/gebietsuebergreifende-zusammenarbeit-vohaben/>

⁶⁵ <https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de/esi-fonds-in-sachsen-anhalt/ueber-die-europaeischen-struktur-und-investitionsfonds/eler/eplr/eler-massnahmen-im-ueberblick/unterstuetzung-der-lokalen-entwicklung-leaderclld/gebietsuebergreifende-zusammenarbeit-vohaben/>

